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Spectrophotometric Determination of Manganese Employing N-Hydroxy-N-phenyl-N'-benzylbenzamide Hydrochloride (HPBBAH)

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FASCINATED by the analytical potentialities of N-hydroxy-N,N'-diarylbenzamidines¹⁻⁵, it was thought worthwhile to synthesise and investigate the complexing properties of a hydroxyamidine analogue in which a methylene group is introduced in between azomethine nitrogen atom and the N'-aryl ring. Thus, in the course of the study, it is found that N-hydroxy-N-phenyl-N'-benzylbenzamide hydrochloride, abbreviated as HPBBAH, reacts with many transition metal ions in a manner analogous to other hydroxyamidines. However, a distinct change in its behaviour with manganese(II) has been noted. Whereas the hydroxyamidines reported earlier^{6,7}, develop a yellow-green colour with manganese(II) in ammoniacal medium⁸, HPBBAH gives an instantaneous and sensitive blue colour in ethanol. Based on this colour reaction, a simple rapid and sensitive spectrophotometric method has been developed for the determination of microgram quantities of manganese.

Experimental

Preparation and the properties of the reagent: HPBBAH was prepared by coupling equimolar ethereal solutions of N-benzylbenzimidoyl chloride and N-phenylhydroxylamine at 0-5° following the general method for the synthesis of hydroxyamidines⁶. The resulting white solid after washing with ether was recrystallised from absolute alcohol containing a few drops of HCl. White shining crystals of the compound melted at 195° (C₂₀H₁₉N₂OCl. requires: C, 70.93; H, 5.61; N, 8.27%, found: C, 70.85; H, 5.76; N, 8.20%)

IR Spectra (nujol-hexachlorobutadiene): ν_{\max} , 2450(=N-H); 1620 (-C=NH); 935 (N-O) cm⁻¹.UV Spectra: $\lambda_{\max}^{\text{EtOH}}$, 213 nm (ϵ , 22500); 300 nm (ϵ , 7050).

A 2% solution of the reagent in ethanol was employed for the development of the colour.

A stock solution of manganese(II) was prepared by dissolving MnCl₂·2H₂O in double distilled water containing few drops of HCl. The solution was standardised complexometrically^{9,10}. Solutions of diverse ions were prepared from analytical grade chemicals.

Infrared and ultraviolet spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 221 and Carl-Zeiss 'Specord' (UV/VIS) spectrophotometers respectively. Absorbance measurements were made with an ECIL GS-865 spectrophotometer equipped with 1 cm matched cuvettes. The pH of the solutions were measured with a Systronic pH meter type 322.

Recommended procedure for the determination of manganese: To a suitable aliquot (1-2 ml) of the solution containing 10-100 μg of the metal, taken in a 10 ml volumetric flask, add 2 ml of the reagent solution. Adjust the pH to 8.4-9.8 with dilute ammonia and allow to stand for 2 min with occasional shaking. Dilute to volume with enough water and ethanol so as to give a final 70% concentration of the latter. Measure the absorbance at 590 nm against alcohol as blank.

Results and Discussion

The instantaneously developed manganese-HPBBAH complex shows an absorption maxima at 590 nm. The reagent has practically no absorbance at 450 nm and above and hence for all photometric measurements alcohol was used as blank. The colour is stable atleast for 2 hr in the temperature range 20-40°. The absorption of the complex remains constant and maximum in the pH range from 8.4 to 9.8. Therefore, a pH value of 9.1 \pm 0.1 was arbitrarily chosen for the spectrophotometric studies. To achieve maximum colour development, a 1 to 80 molar ratio of the metal to reagent is necessary. In practice, for every 100 μg of the metal 40 mg of the reagent was employed. A 1:400 manganese to ligand ratio has been studied to have no adverse effect on the determination. The order of the addition of the reagents is critical.

The system adheres to Beer's law upto 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ of manganese concentration. Ringbom's plot¹¹ suggests an effective metal concentration range of 2.0-9.0 ppm. The molar absorptivity of the complex is 5.33×10^4 litre mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹ at 590 nm (on the basis of the manganese content). The sensitivity of the colour reaction according to Sandell's definition¹² ($\log I_0/I = 0.001$) is 0.0103 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$. Ten independent determinations on solutions each containing 50 μg of Mn(II)/10 ml gave a mean absorbance value of 0.485 and a standard deviation of ± 0.003 or a relative standard deviation of $\pm 0.61\%$. The method is, thus, fairly precise and reproducible.

Interference :

In the determination of 5 ppm of manganese at pH 9.1 ± 0.1 the following ions do not interfere to the extents ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) given in the parentheses: CH_3COO^- , Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , SO_4^{2-} , NO_3^- , or $\text{B}_4\text{O}_7^{2-}$ (500); PO_4^{3-} (100); Na^+ , K^+ , Li^+ , Rb^+ or Cs^+ (500); Ba^{2+} or Sr^{2+} (250); Ag^+ (50); Cd^{2+} (20); MoO_4^{2-} or WO_4^{2-} (20). However, Cu^{2+} , Pd^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Fe^{3+} , VO_3^- , EDTA and fluoride seriously interfere at all concentrations. The use of common masking agents to eliminate their interferences was not fruitful.

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Simultaneous Spectrophotometric Determination of Vanadium and Uranium with 4-Methyl Daphnetin

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VANADIUM and uranium metals are frequently mined together. Although reliable analytical procedures for their determination are known, very little work has appeared on the simultaneous spectrophotometric analysis of these metals.

4-methyl daphnetin forms an orange-yellow complex with uranium (λ_{max} 450 nm) and a bluish-green complex with vanadium (λ_{max} 600 nm) in the pH range 5 and 7. The present work reports a simple and quick simultaneous spectrophotometric method of analysis of vanadium and uranium with 4-methyl daphnetin.

From the spectrophotometric properties of the complexes.

Complex	λ_{max} nm	ϵ_{450}	ϵ_{600}	Sandell sensitivity $\mu\text{g/cm}^2$
V(v)-4-methyl daphnetin	600	6375	900	0.006
U(vi)-4-methyl daphnetin	450	2700	0	0.030

The relationships (1) and (2)

$$A_{450} = \epsilon_{450}^V [V] + \epsilon_{450}^U [U] \quad (1)$$

$$A_{600} = \epsilon_{600}^V [V] + \epsilon_{600}^U [U] \quad (2)$$

were used to develop the following equations :

$$[V] \times 10^4 = 1.266 A_{600}$$

$$[U] \times 10^4 = 3.7 A_{450} - 3.4 A_{600}$$

Several synthetic mixtures were prepared and analysed satisfactorily.

Procedure

To an aliquot containing 0.8 to 1.6 μg of V(v) and 10-25 μg of UO_2^{2+} is added 4 ml of 0.1M alcoholic solution of 4-methyl daphnetin. The pH of the solution is adjusted between 5 and 7 and the resulting solution diluted to 25 ml. The absorbance of the solutions are measured at 450 and 600 nm against the corresponding reagent blank. The amounts of metals are computed from the appropriate simultaneous equations. A large number of anions do not interfere in the estimation, however Mo, Fe, Ti, W interfere and should be eliminated.

Structures of the Reaction Products from Reaction of Resorcinol with N-Benzoyl Phthalimide

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AN organic dye has been synthesised by the condensation of Resorcinol with N-Benzoyl phthalimide which is a known compound. It behaves like florescene, a dye.